

DYNAMICS, TRENDS, AND SOCIOECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF CONFLICT-INDUCED DISPLACED PERSONS IN NORTH-EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: This paper examines the trends, dynamics, and socioeconomic implications of conflict-induced displacement in Northeastern Nigeria. A cross-section survey research design was adopted. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were utilized. The results of the analyses revealed that the four extracted components accounted for 86.3 percent of the total variance observed. The result of the one-way analysis of variance on the extracted components classified as access to basic amenities by the internally displaced with f-values of ($F = 305.676$), livelihood assets ($F = 254.527$), living standard ($F = 172.597$), and poverty status ($F = 125.005$) revealed a significant variation in the socioeconomic impacts of conflict in Northeastern Nigeria at a 0.001 significance level. This implies that loss of livelihood assets, income sources, increased poverty status, number of displaced children, and poor access to basic healthcare are the impacts of conflict-induced displacements in northeastern Nigeria. Consequently, a holistic understanding of the implications of conflict-induced displacement and disruption of livelihoods, employment, housing, health, security, and basic services are vital to providing a sustainable solution to the impacts of displacement on IDPs.

Keywords: Dynamics and trends, conflict-induced displacement, internally displaced, Persons, socio-economic implications, Northeastern Nigeria

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Guiding Principles of Internal Displacement (1998) defined Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) as persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights, or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized

state border. Livelihoods and healthcare are among the first casualties of forced displacement; communities are pushed and displaced from their homes to more sordid levels of poverty and impoverishment. IOM (2016) stated that Northeastern Nigeria witnessed an increase in violence since the beginning of 2014, causing a major humanitarian crisis. Consequently, More than two million individuals have been displaced as a consequence of the intensification of attacks by terrorists, as well as counter-insurgency activities of the Nigerian Government, with the highest number of displacements taking place in Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa States respectively.

The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2004) reported that internal displacement is one of the greatest tragedies of our time and internally displaced persons (IDPs) are among the most vulnerable of the human family. Moreover, IOM (2014) reported that the escalating violence caused by the Boko Haram insurgency in the Northeastern region of Nigeria has led to an increase in the number of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), especially in Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, and Taraba States.

IDMC (2014) reported that 38 million people around the world had been forced to flee their homes due to conflicts fueled by ethnic, religious, and political undertones. Internally displaced persons have increased between 2013 and 2015 to about 5 million within Nigeria. These force-induced flows had a profound and detrimental effect on the livelihoods and health of IDPs and reduced access to healthcare, housing, and basic amenities.

Previous studies such as Durosaro and Ajiboye (2011) examined the problems and coping strategies of internally displaced adolescents in the Jos metropolis, Nigeria. The result showed that educational and emotional problems are most prominent among internally displaced adolescents. In the same vein, Okoli and Iortyer (2014) investigated the humanitarian impact of terrorism in Nigeria from the stand point of the Boko Haram insurgency; the authors affirmed that the Boko Haram insurgency has resulted in a dire humanitarian situation as evident in human casualties, human right abuses, population displacement and refugee debacle, livelihood crisis, and public insecurity. The authors recommend a strategic paradigm shift from anti-terrorism to counter-terrorism as a strategy for containing the crisis.

Moreover, Bala, Azman and Singh (2022) explored the psychological impact of the Boko Haram insurgency on the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The result revealed a statistically significant relationship between Boko Haram insurgency and male and female IDPs in Nasarawa State at a 0.05 significance level. Owoaje et.al., (2016) undertook a scoping review of the health problems of internally displaced persons in Africa. The study revealed that the major physical and health problems and symptoms were fever/malaria (85% in children and 48% in adults) malnutrition in children (stunting 52% and wasting 6%), malnutrition in adult males (24%), diarrhea 62% in children 22% in adults) and acute respiratory infections (45%). Adimula (2016) studied the plight of women and children in Nigeria's IDP camps. Gwadabe, Ahmad and Jamil, (2018) examined forced displacement and the plight of internally displaced persons in Northeast Nigeria.

However, despite all these plethora of studies on internally displaced persons, there is a dearth of research on the dynamics, spatial and temporal trends, and socioeconomic implications of conflict-induced displacements in northeastern Nigeria.

1.1 Factors Influencing Internal Displacement

A multiplicity of reasons could be advanced for internal displacement ranging from natural disasters, armed conflicts, and insurgency. Figure 1 presents the reasons identified for internal displacement.

Figure 1: Map of IDPs in Nigeria

Source: IDMC (2014).

IOM report (2014) revealed that a multiplicity of reasons have been identified for internal displacement, more than 77.1 percent of the IDPs were displaced because of insurgency, while 22.4percent were displaced due to communal clashes, and 0.5percentof the displaced specified natural disasters as the reason for internal displacement. Bamidele and Pikirayi (2023) assessed the livelihoods and daily challenges of internally displaced women (IDW) in the new Kuchingoro Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camp in Abuja, Nigeria. Ben-Edet (2022) examined the impact of insurgencies and security threats caused by Boko Haram and the ISIS terrorist alliance in Nigeria. A review of the literature revealed a dearth of research and limited information on the trends and socio-economic implications (of IDPs) in Nigeria. Hence, more research is required onthe trends and socioeconomic implications of conflict-induced displacements in Nigeria.

This paper is structured thus: the introductory section presents the background to the study, while a conceptual framework of the dynamics and drivers of internal displacement in Nigeria is presented in section 2. Section 3 presents a discussion of research methods and area of study. A discussion of findings on the dynamics and socioeconomic implications of displacements are discussed in section 4. Section 5 concludes with recommendations.

2 TRENDS AND DRIVERS OF INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS IN NIGERIA

A discussion of temporal trends of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) from 2009-2021 and the drivers of conflict-induced displacement in Nigeria are undertaken in this section.

2.1 Temporal Trends of Internal Displacements

Nigeria is a country with a large population that accounted for the highest proportion of internally displaced persons (3.3 million persons) in Africa arising from conflicts and generalized violence. In the north-east geopolitical zone, Borno State had the highest number of IDPs 672, 714 individuals, Adamawa State had 220,159 internally displaced persons, and Yobe State had 135, 810 internally displaced persons.

Table 1: Displacement Matrix of North-East Nigeria

Location/States	IDPs	IDP Households	Average Household Size
Adamawa State	220,159	25, 807	8.5
Bauchi State	60, 555	9, 881	6.1
Borno State	672, 714	76, 842	8.8
Gombe State	24, 655	3, 335	7.4
Taraba State	74, 125	11, 599	6.4
Yobe State	135, 810	21, 893	6.2
Total	1, 188, 018	149, 357	8.0

Source: UNHR (2015)

Information in Table 2 presents the temporal trends of internal displacement from 2009-2021.

In the years 2009 and 2010, 5,000 persons were internally displaced, the displaced persons gradually increased to 65,000 in 2011, 470,000 in 2013, and then peaked in 2014 with 975,000 conflict-induced internally displaced persons and a total of 330,000 conflict-induced displacements. The number of conflict-induced displacements then decreased gradually from 737,000 in 2015 to 279,000 in 2017, increased to 541,000 in 2018, and 376,000 in 2021. Moreover, the total number of conflict-induced displaced persons continues to increase from 3,300,000 in 2013 to 3,228,000 in 2021 (see Table 2).

Table 2: Trends of Internal Displacement (2009-2021)

Year	Total number of IDPs	Conflict Induced Displacements
2009	-	5000
2010	-	5000
2011	-	65000
2012	-	63000
2013	3300000	470000
2014	1075000	975000
2015	2096000	737000
2016	1955000	501000
2017	1707000	279000
2018	2216000	541000
2019	2583000	248000
2020	2730000	169000
2021	3228000	376000

Source: IDMC, Internal Displacement Conflict Data (2009-2021)

2.2 Dynamics and Drivers of Conflict-Induced Displacement

A comprehensive understanding of the dynamics or range of factors that influence displacement is very vital to this study. These drivers and impacts could be linked to human actions such as population dynamics, North-South migration/movement, access to basic amenities including healthcare, corruption and governance issues, lack of investment in basic amenities, high unemployment, livelihood loss, uneven development, and malnutrition, environmental degradation, insecurity, inter-ethnic conflicts and tension between herdsman and farmers. (IOM, 2016) reported that out of the four countries affected (Nigeria, Niger, Cameroon and Chad), Nigeria experienced over two million persons internally displaced in North East Nigeria across 13 states with the highest IDPs located in Borno, Yobe and Adamawa States respectively..

Moreover, over the last 45 years, Lake Chad has shrunk resulting in human impacts such as loss of livelihoods, displacements of pastoralists/herdsman, limited access to water, and putting grazing under strain (University of Leeds, 2014). As seen in several African countries displacement has worsened food insecurity because most farmers are no longer on their farms due to armed attacks and abduction (See Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Dynamics/Drivers of Displacements in Nigeria

Source: Adapted from Interlocking Displacement Drivers in Northeastern Nigeria (2016)

The Drivers of conflict-induced displacement are presented in Figure 2 as the demographic factors which include attributes and dynamics of the population, north-south movements, and limited access to basic amenities experienced by the IDPs. The political factors and drivers of displacement include bad leadership, poor governance, and corruption. The economic drivers of displacement are not limited to unemployment, livelihood loss, under-development, dependency on remittances, and food imports. The environmental drivers of displacement include environmental degradation, pollution, deforestation, and climate variability. The drivers of conflict and violence include insecurity, abduction, inter-ethnic conflicts, and tension between herdsmen and farmers.

UNHRC (2018) reported the trend at a glance that the global population forcibly displaced increased by 2.3 million persons. By the end of the year 2018, 70.8 million individuals were displaced worldwide as a result of persecution, conflict, violence, or human rights violations. The geography of internal displacement as well as the contemporary landscape of internal displacement is changing: over the past decade the global population of forced-displacement persons grew substantially from 43.3 million in 2009 to 70.8 million in 2018, reaching a record high. The number of new displacements was equivalent to an average of 37,000 people being forced to flee their homes every day in 2018.

3. RESEARCH METHODS AND AREA OF STUDY

3.1 Study Area

Gubio is an IDP camp located in the Gubio Local Government Area about 16km from Maiduguri in Borno State. Gubio camp was formally opened in 2015 to receive Nigerian refugees from the Niger Republic. The state is bounded in the north by the Republic of Niger, the Republic of Chad to the northeast, and Cameroon to the east (Figure 2). To southern and western borders are the Adamawa, Gombe, and Yobe states with a population of 4,151,193 and a landmass of 57,799 km² (NPC, 2006). The state is located in the Sudan savanna and a region of the Sahel savanna with sandy soils in the north and swamps in the south and southwest of Lake Chad. The state is drained in the south by River Gongola, a tributary of River Benue (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2018).

Figure 2: The Study Area

Source: Authors' GIS Lab (2022)

3.2 Research Methods

A discussion of the research methods utilized and the area of study are presented in this section.

3.2.1 Sampling Technique

In cases where your survey area is too large (a country, province, or district) or a dispersed population, cluster sampling can be used. In this cluster sampling, the basic units selected within the camp are clusters of males, females, and children. Due to security considerations, this study, therefore, utilized a survey research design involving multi-stage cluster sampling. In the first stage: the Gubio community which is made up of (4,500 IDPs) mainly women and children were purposively chosen due to the vulnerability of the community to BokoHaram attacks. In the second stage: the camp is divided into three distinct clusters of old men, women, and children. Using the rule of thumb of (1 percent) of the IDPs on camp, fifty (50) participants made up of displaced men, women, and children were randomly selected from each cluster for the survey. In the third stage, a structured questionnaire on socio-demographic characteristics (age, gender, school enrollment, losses experienced, income, livelihoods and health status) and the impact of conflict-induced displacement was administered to the respondents selected from each cluster. Frequency tables and charts, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA) were utilized to examine the variation in the socioeconomic implications of conflict-induced displacement on internally displaced persons (IDPs).

4. RESULTS AND RESEARCH FINDINGS

A discussion of results and test of the hypothesis that there is significant variation in socio-economic implications of conflict-induced displacement among the IDPs in is presented in this section. The findings reveal that the IDP camp in the Gubio community is made up of an 80percentmixed population of children, women, men, and the aged that have experienced the loss of occupation and livelihoods. The crisis fuelled the North-South movement of displaced persons away from their homes. The IDPs lack access to functional basic amenities, increased the number of out-of-school children, worsen mental-health related issues, experienced high unemployment, loss of farmlands/livelihoods, malnutrition, environmental degradation, increased inter-ethnic conflicts and tension between herdsman and farmers. This armed conflict displacement has worsened food insecurity because most farmers are no longer on their farms due to armed attacks, abduction, and destruction of lives and properties at will. The insurgents destroyed the lives, properties, and livelihoods of the displaced persons making it difficult for the IDPs to be economically active and worse off.

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Selected Displaced Persons

The profile of the displaced persons examined includes gender, occupation/means of livelihood, change in income level, and school enrolment. Findings revealed that 34.0percent of the participants are males, while females represent 66.0percent. Twelve percent were civil servants, 30.0 percent were farmers, 42.0percent were involved in business activities and trades, and 8.0percent depended on domestic remittances and financial assistance from relatives and friends. After the displacement, 40.0percent of the respondents indicate that there was an improvement in income earned, while 52.0percent indicate a decline in income earned due to livelihoods and assets losses, while 20.0percent claimed that some informal productive economic activities increased due to internal displacements, while 80.0percent claimed formal productive economic activities reduced due to internal displacements, livelihoods, and assets loss, while 36.0percent indicates that their children are out of school due to conflict-induced displacements, loss of livelihoods, destruction of facilities, insecurity and ill-health as a result of communicable diseases and mental health issues necessitating the need for adaptation of healthcare services (see Table 2).

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	17	34.0
female	33	66.0
total	50	100
Livelihoods/Income source	Frequency	Percentage
Civil servant	6	12.0
Farmers	15	30.0
Foresters	4	8.0
Traders	21	42.0
Domestic remittances	4	8.0
Total	50	100
Change in Income	Frequency	Percentage
Better	20	40.0
Same	4	8.0
Worse	26	52.0
Total	50	100
Ownership of Assets	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	33	66.0
No	17	34.0
Economic Activities	Frequency	Percentage
Decreased Eco. Activities Increased Eco. Activities	10	20.0
Total	40	80.0
Total	50	100
Children in School	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	21	42.0
No	18	36.0
No Response	11	22.0
Total	50	100

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2022)

Table 3: Principal Component Analysis

Variables	Components			
Valid	1	2	3	4
Poverty status	0.105	-0.191	-0.179	0.844
Income status	0.046	-0.209	0.914	0.033
Own assets	-0.200	0.798	-0.137	-0.209
Livelihoods	-0.122	0.345	0.905	-0.016
Electricity	0.513	-0.733	-0.195	0.191
Water	0.898	0.051	-0.165	0.245
Enrolment in school	0.096	-0.031	0.648	0.600
Health issues	0.953	-0.191	0.051	-0.003
Health facilities	-0.045	0.186	0.465	0.804
Number of children	-0.556	0.105	-0.038	-0.594
Gender	-0.953	0.191	-0.051	0.003
Income source	-0.339	0.735	0.456	-0.049
Cooking fuel	-0.377	-0.826	0.100	-0.365
Eigen Value	4.552	3.200	2.015	1.461
Percent Variance (percent)	35.017	24.615	15.498	11.240
Cumulative Explanation (percent)	35.017	59.633	75.131	86.371

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2022)

4.2 The Influence of Socio-economic characteristics on (IDPs)

This section focused on the social and economic sub-systems such as basic amenities, livelihood assets, living standards, and poverty status of IDPs. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and ANOVA were utilized to examine the variations in the socio-economic implications of conflict-induced displacement on the IDPs. At first, four main principal components which explained 86.3 percent of the total variance were extracted based on the eigenvalue of more than one (>1). The first component explained 35.1 percent, followed by the second component 24.6 percent, the third component 15.5 percent, and the fourth component 11.2 percent.

The first component extracted is highly and positively correlated with electricity with a coefficient of (0.513), water quality (0.898), and health status (0.953), and negatively correlated with gender and number of children, with a coefficient of gender (-0.953) and increased number of children (-0.556), women and children are usually the victims of internal displacement. This first component could be classified as access to basic amenities.

The second component extracted correlates positively with ownership of livelihood assets with a coefficient of (0.798) and income source (0.735). This second component could be categorized as means of livelihood. The third component extracted is positively correlated income assets and school enrolment with a component loading

of (0.914) for income, livelihood assets (0.905), and school enrolment (0.648). This third component could be classified as the living standard of households. The fourth principal component extracted on the one hand had a high and positive coefficient loading with poverty status (0.844), access to education (0.600), and access to healthcare facilities (0.804), while on the other hand, this fourth extracted component had a negative coefficient loading with an increased number of children (-0.594). This fourth component extracted could be classified as the welfare status of the respondents.

The information in Table 4 presents the result of ANOVA which showed that access to basic amenities by the IDPs had an f-value of (F= 305.676), livelihood assets (F = 254.527), living standard (F = 172.597), and poverty status (F= 125.005), and revealed a significant variation in the implications of conflict-induced displacements at 0.001 significant level. This implies that limited access to basic amenities, loss of livelihood assets, and income sources, increased poverty status, and increased number of displaced children have significant implications on the displaced persons in Nigeria.

Table 4: One-way analysis of variance

Extracted Components	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Basic Amenities	Regression	6.328	1	6.328	305.676
	Residual	0.642	31	0.021	
	Total	6.970	32		
2 Livelihood Asset	Regression	6.582	2	3.291	254.527
	Residual	0.388	30	0.013	
	Total	6.970	32		
3 Living Standard	Regression	6.600	3	2.200	172.597
	Residual	0.370	29	0.013	
	Total	6.970	32		
4 Poverty Level	Regression	6.600	4	1.650	125.005
	Residual	0.370	28	0.013	
	Total	6.970	32		

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2022)

5. CONCLUSION

The study examined the trends and dynamics of conflict-induced displacement in northeastern Nigeria. Internal displacement is a highly dynamic phenomenon that affects the socio-economics of displaced persons in diverse ways. A survey research design involving clustered sampling was adopted, and a quantitative technique involving the Principal Component Analysis and Analysis of Variance was utilized. The result of the PCA revealed that 86.3 percent of the total variance was explained by the extracted components. Basic amenities with an f-value of (305.676), livelihood assets (F = 254.527), living standard (f = 172.597), and poverty status (F = 125.005) revealed a significant variation in the dynamics of conflict-induced displacements in northeastern Nigeria at 0.001 level of significance. This result implies that limited access to basic amenities, loss of livelihood assets and income

sources, increased poverty level, and increased number of displaced children are the dynamics of conflict-induced displacement in northeastern Nigeria. Subsequently, there is need for a proactive governance, improved welfare, and access to basic amenities in the IDP camps.

REFERENCES

- Adekola, P. O., Azuh, D., Amoo, E. O., & Brownell, G. (2019). Restoration of water supply in post-conflict communities in Nigeria and sustainable re-integration. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*, 10, 191–201. Retrieved from <http://www.iaeme.com/ijciat/issues.asp?JType=IJCIET&VType=10&IType=02>
- Adimula, B. (2016). Opinion: The plight of women and children in Nigeria's IDP camps. Retrieved from <http://ynaija.com/idp-women-children/>
- Anzellini, V., & Leduc, C. (2019). Research coordinator, Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/05/the-number-of-internally-displaced-people-is-at-a-record-high-heres-why/>
- Bala, N. A., Azman, A., & Singh, P. S. J. (2022). The psychological impact of terrorism on internally displaced persons in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Art & Social Science Research*, 12(1), 179–200.
- Bamidele, S., & Pikirayi, I. (2023). Who hears the cry of the wailing women?: Discourses on livelihood activities and challenges of internally displaced women in Nigeria. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 25(1), 1–16.
- Ben-Edet, E. (2022). Terrorism: A case study of the global security threat of Boko Haram and ISIS alliance in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://digitalscholarship.tsu.edu/dissertations/8>
- Cantor, D., Swartz, J., Roberts, B., Abbara, A., Ager, A., Bhutta, Z. A., Blanchet, K., Bunte, D. M., Chukwuorji, J. C., Daoud, N., Ekezie, W., Jimenez-Damary, C., Jobanputra, K., Makhshvili, N., Rayes, D., Restrepo-Espinosa, M. H., Rodriguez-Morales, A. J., Salami, B., & Smith, J. (2021). Understanding the health needs of internally displaced persons: A scoping review. *Journal of Migration and Health*, 4, 100071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmh.2021.100071>
- Deola, C., & Patel, R. B. (2014). Health outcomes of crisis-driven urban displacement: A conceptual framework. *Disaster Health*, 2(2), 92–96.
- Donner, W., & Rodríguez, H. (2008). Population composition, migration, and inequality: The influence of demographic changes on disaster risk and vulnerability. *Social Forces*, 87(2), 1089–1114.

Durosaro, I. A., & Ajiboye, S. K. (2011). Problems and coping strategies of internally displaced adolescents in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(20), 256–262.

Encyclopaedia Britannica. (2018). *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Retrieved from www.britannica.com/place/Borno

Gao, W., Wang, Y., Liu, Z., & Wang, X. (2007). A study on depression characteristics and its influencing factors in children left in rural areas. *ZhongguoXingweiYixueKexue* (Chinese Journal of Behavioral Medical Science), 16(3), 238–240.

Getanda, E. M., Papadopoulous, C., & Evans, H. (2015). The mental health, quality of life and life satisfaction of internally displaced persons living in Nakuru Country, Kenya. *BMC Public Health*, 15, 755.

Human Rights Watch. (2018). By day we fear the army, by night the jihadists: Abuses by armed Islamists and security forces in Burkina Faso, May 21, 2018.

ICRC. (2018). *I saw my city die: The human toll of urban warfare*, June 15, 2017; ICRC, *Displaced in cities: Experiencing and responding to urban internal displacement outside camps*, August 16, 2018.

Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC). (2012). *Internal displacement in Africa: A development challenge*. Geneva: IDMC.

Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC). (2016). *Global report on internal displacement (GRID Report)*. Geneva: IDMC.

Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC). (2019). *Global report on internal displacement*. Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre and Norwegian Refugee Council. Retrieved from <http://www.internal-displacement.org/global-report/grid2019/>

International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2014). *Displacement Tracking Matrix Report (DTM, 2014)*. Geneva: IOM.

International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2015). *The World Migration Report 2015: Migrants and cities, new partnerships to manage mobility*. Geneva: IOM.

International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2016). Nigeria Emergency Operations. Situation report June 2016. Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/IOM-Nigeria-Emergency-Operations-Situation-Report-April-2016.pdf>

- Jia, Z., & Tian, W. (2010). Loneliness of left-behind children: A cross-sectional survey in a sample of rural China. *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 36(6), 812–817.
- Lee, E. S. (1966). A theory of migration. *Demography*, 3(1), 47–57.
- Mooney, E. (2005). The concept of internal displacement and cases for internally displaced persons as a category of concern. *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, 24(3), 9–26.
- Myerson, R. (2015). Human capital and China's left-behind migrant children: Policy analysis with endogenous migration decisions. Working Paper, University of Chicago, IL, Chicago.
- National Population Commission (NPC). (2006). *The Nigeria population census (2006)*. Retrieved from http://www.population.gov.ng/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=89
- NEMA, SEMA, & IOM. (2014). *The IDP situation in north-eastern Nigeria (Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe, Taraba, Yobe): Displacement Tracking Matrix Report (DTM)*.
- Nigeria Emergency Operations (IOM). (2016). *Regional response situation report*, April 2016.
- Norwegian Refugee Council. (2016). Norwegian Refugee Council Nigeria-Fact Sheet. *Global report on internal displacement (GRID)*, 8–13.
- Ferris, E. (2012). Internal displacement in Africa: An overview of trends and opportunities. In *Brookings-LSE Project on Internal Displacement – Conference*, Arlington, 1–12.
- OCHA. (1998). *Guiding principles on internal displacement*. <https://www.internal-displacement.org/sites/default/files/publications/documents/199808-training-OCHA-guiding-principles-Eng2.pdf>
- Okoli, A. C., & Iortyer, P. (2014). Terrorism and humanitarian crisis in Nigeria: Insights from Boko Haram insurgency. *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Political Science*, 14(1), 39–49.
- Owoaje, E. T., Uchendu, O. C., Ajayi, T. O., & Cadmus, E. O. (2017). A review of the health problems of the internally displaced persons in Africa. *Nigerian Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 23(4), 161–171.
- Porter, M., & Haslam, N. (2005). Pre-displacement and post-displacement factors associated with the mental health of refugees and internally displaced persons: A meta-analysis. *JAMA*, 294, 602–612.

- Raji, S., Adekayaoja, F. A., Agaku, E. A., Akujobi, J. A., & Hamzat, A. (2021). Northeastern Nigeria: Assessing the response capacity of National Emergency Management Agency to the plights of internally displaced persons. *Heliyon*, 7(6), e07274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07274>
- Salami, B., Iwuagwu, S., & Amodu, O. (2020). The health of internally displaced children in sub-Saharan Africa: A scoping review. *BMJ Global Health*, 5, e002584.
- UN. (2011). *Guiding principles on internal displacement: The AU Convention for the Protection and Assistance of IDPs in Africa*.
- United Nations Human Rights. (2015). *Displacement tracking matrix: Round IV report*, June 2015.
- UNICEF Nigeria. (2016). *Consolidated Emergency Report (CMR)*. UNICEF Nigeria/Naftalin.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). (2016). *Global trends: Forced displacement in 2015*. Geneva: UNHCR.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). (2018). *Global trends: Forced displacement in 2018*. Geneva: UNHCR.
- United Nations Human Rights. (2015). *Displacement tracking matrix: Round IV report*, June 2015.
- WFP, FAO & IFAD. (2017). *The state of food security and nutrition in Nigeria: Building resilience for peace and food security*.